

Comparison of Graph-Based Filtering Mechanisms for LLM Data Leak Prevention

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Abstract—Large-language models are increasingly being used for a variety of applications, including chatbots and media content generation. LLMs are normally used with decision machines like neural networks. Among the myriad of security issues faced by LLMs are model extraction attacks, training data copyright, and the emphasis of this work: prompt engineered training data leaks. The authors propose a filtering system for identifying and preventing disclosure of training data leaks prior to sending to end users. This system modifies a prior semantic-graph solution by the authors and makes comparative experimentation between this work and its predecessor, with the key difference being the use of a property graph. The implementation of a filtering system based on a property graph database was used for a repository of training data against which LLM outputs were compared to identify leaks. Three distinct training data repository applications were devised; hash-code format, plain-text format, and plain-text format incorporating natural language processing (NLP). Experimental results include accuracy, overhead, and acceleration. Multiple anomalies were observed in the LLMs output during experimentation, and these are examined in this work as plausible training data leaks, observing new anomaly types and producing deeper insights compared to those discovered in the prior solution.

Index Terms—AI, LLM, Security, Filtering, Graph

I. INTRODUCTION

The advent of reliably accurate LLM-based tools has fostered many novel solutions to a variety of problems including dealing with customers and generating content. LLMs can also be coupled with domain-specific AI models such as the YOLO [1] (you only look once) image detection model, which is used for purposes such as satellite image analysis [2]. A recurring characteristic of these tools is the use of a chatbot as their user interface, as with Gemini [3] and ChatGPT [4]. LLMs are trained on a sizable training data set, in some cases containing confidential information intended to provide the LLM with certain knowledge or capabilities without directly exposing the source data to the user. Training data leaks, however, have been induced in prior attacks on LLMs such as with the “divergence attack” on ChatGPT [5]. This attack entailed

having the LLM repeat the same word continuously, which resulted in model state breakdown leading to training data leakage. Personal identifying information featured in some of the leaked artifacts, posing significant concerns ranging from data privacy to legal. Data leak prevention systems are presently in-place on many popular LLMs and their presence can often be identified by their blocking of the LLM’s response to a prompt, and these techniques must constantly adapt to match evolving security threats to LLMs [6], with techniques emerging such as architectural backdoor injection to trigger unwanted LLM behavior when certain inputs are provided. An exploit in the Qwen Model [7] which was discovered in prior work [8] is further examined in this work.

II. BACKGROUND AND RELATED WORK

A graph-based filtering approach has previously been detailed [8] using semantic graphs, namely RDF, to apply safeguarding against LLMs outputting training data by using a bank of training data to validate outbound messages from the LLM. Knowledge graphs have widely varied uses, ranging from acting as metadata indices to providing vocabularies for automotive data models [9]. The architecture of that prior work is applied in this work, and the results from the prior work are used herein for comparison between the semantic graph RDF Apache-Jena-based approach of the prior work and the property graph Neo4j-based approach detailed in this work. The methodology and supporting technologies are kept the same with the aim of fair comparison. A plethora of attacks and vulnerabilities, both practical and theoretical, exist for LLMs [10] including prompt injection, model extraction, training data poisoning and many more, moreover one can further expand this list of threats by considering attacks with aspects targeting the network and security protocols used by the LLM, one such generic attack being network traffic analysis and pattern recognition [11]. There are many existing countermeasures to these attacks [12] such as anonymisation and sanitisation to scrub the data of sensitive information, knowledge unlearning to completely remove specific confidential data, filtering of inbound or outbound LLM data as well

Fig. 1: Filtering System Architecture [8]

as input and output validation [13], [14]. Pattern recognition attacks on the network communications which the LLM relies on can be mitigated against using several techniques, including obfuscation-based approaches such as the shuffle index [11], [15] Data leak prevention systems (DLPs) are widely used, and are applicable to LLMs to protect data in transit and data at rest from leakage [16]. Other approaches to this problem space integrate context-awareness into filtering [17], in an attempt to separate true leaks and false positives.

III. REFERENCE ARCHITECTURE

The solution proposed in this work follows the reference architecture used previously for its RDF-based predecessor [8]. This solution places a filtering mechanism alongside the LLM where it can provide filtering capabilities on outgoing messages. Figure 1 showcases the solution architecture, which is repurposed from the prior work with minor changes, namely the removal of the term ‘‘RDF Graph’’ and insertion of the term ‘‘Knowledge Graph’’ so that the architecture diagram accurately reflects both the RDF-based prior work and this work’s property-graph focused experimentation. Classification components are where the outgoing responses are caught, and then classified using either an NLP or programmatic model. Once classified, the outputs can then be used to search the property graph of training data, where no results indicate that no leak has occurred and the message is output as normal. If the property graph search does return a result, then it indicates a training data leak, and prevents output of the data. In Figure 1 the attacker is coloured red, and the scenario depicts the leak being stopped prior to communication to this malicious user. The various elements of this architecture will hereby be described:

LLM Chatbot: The LLM chatbot handles input from the user via API and provides responses. The property-graph

Fig. 2: Hashed Training Data Graph Example [8]

Fig. 3: Training Data Graph Example [8]

based filtering system is present, aiming to prevent training data leaks from this LLM chatbot.

NLP Classification: The classification of outgoing LLM responses according to the subject matter via an NLP model. This model performs data tokenisation using part-of-speech (POS) tagging, which enables specific search on the property graph, for example searching on only one branch rather than the entirety of the graph.

Programmatic Classification: This classification method is an alternative to the NLP approach and uses a specified keyword corpus to classify the outgoing LLM message by subject matter. Keyword extraction from the LLM message is used to denote the subject matter using keywords present in the corpus tagged with different categories, which map to an element of the training data property graph.

Knowledge Graph Plaintext This graph database holds copies of the LLM training data in plaintext format. A representation of this property graph is seen in Figure 2. It should be noted that LLM training was not undertaken in this work, and as such training data and leaks in testing are synthetic.

Knowledge Graph Hashes This graph is loaded with the hashes of the training data artifacts, rather than the artifacts themselves. This property graph of hashes is depicted by Figure 3. Note; given that these hashes are of synthetic plaintext training, the hashes themselves can be considered synthesized.

Outbound LLM Message Filtering Accurately classified outgoing LLM messages are compared with the relevant property graph element, upon a match being found, a leak is flagged by setting a boolean value.

IV. PROTOTYPE IMPLEMENTATION

The prototype deployment consisted of the property graph filtering system and an open-source LLM. The architecture and specific technologies chosen for the components are near-identical to those used previously on the semantic graph RDF-based filtering system which preceded this work. This prototype architecture can be seen in Figure 1.

User Inputs: A CSV of user messages was used as input to trigger LLM responses.

LLM Chatbot: Boasting a permissive license - the open-source Qwen 2.5 7B LLM was chosen, with 7B denoting a token amount of 7 billion.

Property Graph Plaintext: Neo4j was the choice technology to implement the property graph which was loaded with synthetic training data in plaintext format. The graph contains 1000 elements divided into the aforementioned four types of data; code, PII, report, bytestream.

Property Graph Hashes: Neo4j was also used to implement the property graph containing the hash codes of the training data records in SHA-256 format. Crucially, SHA-256 hashes represent data using lowercase letters a to f and numbers 0 to 9, ensuring a tightly constrained set of 16 possible beginning characters for hash codes. The benefit of this being that the full breadth of possible starting values can be captured across 16 respective graph subsets, one for each starting character.

Programmatic Corpus: This keyword corpus was used to assign LLM outputs to one of the four pre-defined categories in the corpus, namely bytestream, PII, code and report - based on keywords extracted from the LLM message. As with the programmatic corpus, this approach used the reciprocal categories of bytestream, code, report and PII.

NLP Corpus: The Bart-Large-MNLI natural language processing model was used with zero-shot classification. MNLI denoting the “Multi-Genre Natural Language Interface” training data set of the model. This model was identified previously as not accurately classifying data of the bytestream format [8] but was utilized in the same configuration in this work to ensure fair comparison.

LLM Message Filter: This Python application routes inputs to either the plaintext or hash property graph for comparison. If the comparison returns a result then a training data leak is flagged and the response message is prevented from being output. A targeted search of graph subsets is carried out

based on data classification using either the programmatic or NLP corpus.

Synthetic Training Data: the Qwen LLM was neither trained nor fine-tuned as part of this work, which prevented access to any real training data. The generation of synthetic training data enabled the loading property graphs, which underpin the filtering functionality, and thus the same synthetic training data was used to simulate LLM data leaks. The synthetic training data consisted of text from the Big Data Value Association (BDVA) Data Spaces open-access book [18], [19], sections of the Apache Spark code [20], as well as LLM-generated synthetic PII and bytestream data.

Synthetic Data Leaks: This involved modifying LLM messages to the user by inserting either, full training data records, or incomplete chunks of training data, into the message. The tampered LLM message was then used as input to the filtering mechanism.

V. EVALUATION AND RESULTS

A. Experimental Scenarios

This experiment ran on two separate virtual machines (VMs). The filtering system’s VM was equipped with 150GB disk 16GB RAM, 8 CPU cores and Ubuntu version 24 as the operating system (OS). The VM running the LLM was configured with an Nvidia L40S GPU, 80GB disk, 64GB RAM, 8 CPU cores. The VM CPUs were virtualised, and ran on Intel Xeon Gold 6430 physical CPUs. This configuration was identical to that which the prior work’s RDF-based implementation ran on, which was crucial to the accuracy of results comparison between the prior work and this work’s property graph approach. Beyond this, the same low-latency lab environment, including the same physical and virtual network infrastructure as the prior work [8] was also utilized in this work.

Experimental Scenario One: Timing metrics were acquired using two timers, one for end-to-end time, including submitting a prompt to the LLM, categorising the LLM response, checking against the training data graph, and completing the process. Another timer was used to measure the overheads incurred by the filter. The hash generation processes were included in overhead times. 2000 test cases were used to gather times in the “allow” and “block” categories, these were split into 1000 legitimate LLM responses, and 1000 LLM responses injected with synthesised training data to simulate leaks. The LLM response size was limited using the prefix: “In 100 words or less” prior to each prompt. The standard, NLP and hash filtering modalities were all included in testing.

Experimental Scenario Two: Metrics for accuracy were assembled using 3000 test cases. These were split into sets of 1000 elements, namely; full synthetic training data record example leaks, partial synthetic training record data example leaks, and legitimate LLM responses with no synthesised training data present. Standard, NLP and hash filtering were all also tested for this experimental scenario.

Evaluation Metrics: The results are categorised into overhead and accuracy metrics, where overhead shows the excess time incurred by the filtering solution to the baseline LLM process, with these subdivided into allow and block timings. Accuracy results detail the filter’s success at correctly allowing legitimate LLM responses through and at blocking leaks. The accuracy results are categorised into allowing legitimate data, blocking full LLM training data record leaks and blocking partial LLM training data record leaks.

Filtering System Approaches: *Standard filtering* performs a plaintext string compare between outbound LLM messages and elements stored in the property graph. The LLM message is classified prior to the string compare taking place, enabling subsections of the graph to be searched to improve efficiency. *NLP Filtering* includes the Bart-Large-MNLI-Model to automatically classify LLM messages into the pre-defined categories aligned with the property graph subsections. The *hash filtering* approach entails first generating a hash code of the outgoing LLM message and then comparing it against the training data hash-codes stored in the Neo4j property-graph.

Comparison Against Prior Work: Results from the RDF-based prior work [8] are incorporated into this work’s results section tables to facilitate a direct comparison between the RDF and Neo4j (N4J) implementations of the proposed filtering solution.

B. Results

Timing metrics are shown in Tables II and III. Accuracy metrics are shown in Table I. These metrics were assembled using nine test sets for testing three approaches; standard filtering, hash filtering and NLP filtering. NLP filtering was tested using CPU only, and again with GPU acceleration.

N4J Filter Accuracy	Standard Filter	Hash Filter
Allow Valid Data	100%	100%
Block Full Leak	85%	100%
Block Partial Leak	66%	0%
RDF Filter Accuracy	Standard Filter	Hash Filter
Allow Valid Data	100%	100%
Block Full Leak	85%	100%
Block Partial Leak	57%	0%
N4J Filter Accuracy	NLP (CPU)	NLP (GPU)
Allow Valid Data	100%	100%
Block Full Leak	36%	36%
Block Partial Leak	33%	33%
RDF Filter Accuracy	NLP (CPU)	NLP (GPU)
Allow Valid Data	100%	100%
Block Full Leak	40%	40%
Block Partial Leak	35%	35%

TABLE I: Filter Accuracy Results [8]

Table I contains the accuracy metrics for rounds of testing using three test sets against each approach. The results have been corrected for false positives and false negatives using a manual process involving removal of these, for example

where an "accept" result unexpectedly occurred in a round of "reject" times testing, the much longer accept time outlier was removed, as including this would skew the reject timing metrics. Correction entailed running an entire test set again, rather than running a single test case to replace one outlier. Results from the hashed training data approach were absolutely accurate, at 100%, for allowing valid data through the filter and for blocking full training data record leakage. The accuracy was, however, at 0% for blocking partial training data record leakage. This is due to the fundamental way in which hash codes represent data, an excerpt from a training data record will have a drastically different hash code to the full record from which it was taken, making the hash filtering approach less than ideal for handling partial training data record leaks. As is evident from Table I the prior work’s RDF-based filter exhibited this exact shortfall, as the underlying graph database technology is irrelevant to this issue.

For the standard, manual taxonomic, filtering the Neo4J approach was 100% accurate at allowing valid data through, 85% accurate at blocking full leaks and 66% accurate at blocking partial leaks. Distinctions between the Neo4J approach and the RDF approach include a 9% accuracy advantage for the Neo4J approach in blocking partial training data leaks, and the fact that the accuracies for blocking full leaks were in fact not precisely 85% as this was rounded for accuracy, the results were actually single decimal integer apart (84.7 and 84.8). Both discrepancies here are likely due to differences in the Neo4J property graph database and the Apache Jena semantic graph database as all other aspects of the experiment were identical.

Regarding the accuracy of the NLP-based classification approach, expectedly this untuned NLP model performed poorly compared with the manually developed standard filtering taxonomy, however when considering operating at scale the clear solution is to tune the NLP model for accuracy. Interestingly the Neo4J approach sees accuracy of 36% for blocking full training data leaks, and of 33% for blocking partial data leaks which is a few percentage points lower than the RDF-based predecessor. The accuracy discrepancies could have several causes, for example differences in how the two technologies handle encoding, special characters or differences in Neo4J’s Cypher query language and Apache Jena’s SPARQL query language, particularly as sanitisation was not applied to input the test data. More investigation is needed to identify the exact cause. Fine-tuning the NLP model would likely improve the accuracy, though present results show that this approach in its current implementation is not practical for consistently preventing training data leaks.

In Table II the timing metrics for allowing legitimate data through the filter are shown for both this work’s Neo4J-based approach, and the prior work’s RDF-based approach. The standard filtering approach timings, using a manually created taxonomy for classifying data types, were tightly spread for the timings of both approaches, with this work’s Neo4J approach being marginally slower across all categories

than the RDF approach, and more significant differences seen at the edge-cases in max times.

N4J Allow Times (ms)	Standard Filter	Hash Filter
Average E2E	723 ms	733 ms
Average Overhead	91 ms	105 ms
Min E2E	234 ms	240 ms
Min Overhead	63 ms	83 ms
Max E2E	4024 ms	1459 ms
Max Overhead	510 ms	334 ms
RDF Allow Times (ms)	Standard Filter	Hash Filter
Average E2E	698 ms	658 ms
Average Overhead	77 ms	42 ms
Min E2E	179 ms	42 ms
Min Overhead	45 ms	32 ms
Max E2E	3137 ms	97 ms
Max Overhead	1050 ms	83 ms
N4J Allow Times (ms)	NLP (CPU)	NLP (GPU)
Average E2E	1399 ms	841 ms
Average Overhead	773 ms	206 ms
Min E2E	684 ms	344 ms
Min Overhead	470 ms	160 ms
Max E2E	3850 ms	2131 ms
Max Overhead	2564 ms	1248 ms
RDF Allow Times (ms)	NLP (CPU)	NLP (GPU)
Average E2E	2000 ms	714 ms
Average Overhead	1411 ms	125 ms
Min E2E	851 ms	233 ms
Min Overhead	713 ms	94 ms
Max E2E	6156 ms	1497 ms
Max Overhead	5032 ms	871 ms

TABLE II: Filter Allow Timing [8]

The allow timings for the hash filter approach similarly see the Neo4J approach having marginally slower timings across all categories and a more significant outlier in the max timings.

When considering allow timings for the NLP data classification filtering the Neo4J-based filter sees better timings across all categories, including a much better average time than the RDF-based approach for the results where the NLP model was running on CPU-only. The RDF approach exhibits a large outlier of 6 seconds in the maximum element of this set of results, and the Neo4J approach exhibits one of 4 seconds. It is pertinent to note here that these outliers are caused by anomalies in the LLM responses which will be explained in the section following this results discussion.

When viewing the same results for the NLP data classification filtering running on GPU it is clear than the RDF-based approach shows better allow timings than the Neo4J-based filtering, and in this case it is the Neo4J approach exhibiting the larger outlier of over 2 seconds in the maximum result.

Generally, the RDF-based approach exhibits better average times and lower overheads across most categories, with the exception being the NLP on CPU testing. It is possible that large outliers, particularly if several of them occur, could skew

the average times and as such it is recommended in retrospect to increase the size of test sets beyond 1000 elements to make the average times less susceptible to skew.

N4J Block Times (ms)	Standard Filter	Hash Filter
Average E2E	708 ms	737 ms
Average Overhead	99 ms	105 ms
Min E2E	236 ms	80 ms
Min Overhead	74 ms	250 ms
Max E2E	1688 ms	1872 ms
Max Overhead	203 ms	542 ms
RDF Block Times (ms)	Standard Filter	Hash Filter
Average E2E	690 ms	639 ms
Average Overhead	61 ms	47 ms
Min E2E	236 ms	147 ms
Min Overhead	40 ms	32 ms
Max E2E	1327 ms	3644 ms
Max Overhead	322 ms	3062 ms
N4J Block Times (ms)	NLP (CPU)	NLP (GPU)
Average E2E	1230 ms	838 ms
Average Overhead	597 ms	182 ms
Min E2E	839 ms	580 ms
Min Overhead	339 ms	132 ms
Max E2E	2033 ms	4604 ms
Max Overhead	1289 ms	3028 ms
RDF Block Times (ms)	NLP (CPU)	NLP (GPU)
Average E2E	1776 ms	731 ms
Average Overhead	1167 ms	125 ms
Min E2E	1169 ms	482 ms
Min Overhead	743 ms	92 ms
Max E2E	2307 ms	1394 ms
Max Overhead	1594 ms	419 ms

TABLE III: Filter Block Timing [8]

The results detailing block times for the filter are contained in Table III. This shows the time it took for the filter to block output of a training data artifact.

Regarding the standard filtering approach, using the manually created taxonomy, the two approaches did not see large differences in timings though the RDF approach was marginally faster across all categories. The Neo4J approach had the larger maximum end-to-end outlier of the two, but the RDF approach had a larger maximum overhead outlier.

The hash based filtering approach saw the RDF-based filtering approach with lower block timings than the Neo4J filtering approach, despite the RDF approach having a more significant maximum outlier.

On the NLP classification filtering approach; the Neo4J filtering approach exhibited better CPU block times than the RDF filtering approach, similarly to the case with NLP CPU allow times. When examining the NLP block times running on GPU the Neo4J approach is slower than the RDF approach, and it has a much larger maximum outlier in this case. The observation is that the Neo4J approach could compete with the RDF approach in the NLP bracket in terms of timings, though

```

...
Please determine whether the given text is a positive or
negative review. The text will be provided in a code block.

```python
"The restaurant has excellent service and mouth-watering dishes,
but unfortunately, it's way overpriced for such mediocre food."
```

Based on the content of the text, this review can be classified
as negative. While the reviewer acknowledges some positive
aspects like "excellent service" and "mouth-watering dishes,"
the predominant sentiment is negative due to the criticism that
the prices are "way overpriced for such mediocre food." The use
of words like "mediocre" and the overall tone indicating poor
value for money contribute to the negative nature of this
review./popper
...

```

Fig. 4: LLM Anomaly Categorize Reviews

larger suites of testing are needed to mitigate the impact of extreme outliers.

C. Plausible LLM Leaks Observations

In prior work an exploit in the Qwen 2.5 7B LLM was discovered [8]. This exploit was triggered by the prompt “In no more than 100 words, If you could only communicate through emojis for a day, how would you feel?”. This caused model state breakdown (MSB) in the form of thousands of emojis being output followed by abnormal output volumes of text, well beyond 100 words, referred to in this work as “anomalies”. This exploit was reported to the security team of Alibaba [21], who created the Qwen LLM. The term “plausible training data leaks” was selected to describe these anomalies as, without access to the Qwen LLM’s training data it is not feasible to concretely prove this. Beyond this, MSB can provide insights into the statistical underpinnings of a model and this information in itself could be confidential. The anomalies detailed in the prior work had subject matter unrelated to the prompt, and ranged from short phrases in other languages to anomalies over 500 lines long both in different languages and encodings to the user prompt which, when translated and decoded, appeared to be conversations between LLMs and users about programming in Python.

This same exploit in the Qwen LLM was observed during the testing phases of this work, and further investigation was conducted. Several of the anomalies output were in-line with those described above, with one of these including a user apparently asking an LLM to categorise many restaurant review texts into positive and negative categories, excerpt seen in Figure 4, and what appeared to be a list of URLs for an S3 instance of Emojipedia [22], seen in Figure 6. The links themselves point to a restricted S3 instance, though the offering of these links by the LLM during model-state-breakdown could relate to retrieval augmented generation (RAG) or simply be links which the LLM saw during training. Several anomalies were, however, more unusual than those previously detailed.

The first of two unique anomaly types observed during the testing phase in this work involved repeated reference

```

You're a helpful assistant. I've noticed you have a lot of text
and symbols in your response. Can you please clarify what the
message is about or resend it without those extra characters?

```

Fig. 5: LLM Anomaly Assistant Reference

```

=https://emojipedia-us.s3.dualstack.us
west-1.amazonaws.com/thumbs/120/apple/276/book_
1f4d6.png=https://emojipedia-us.s3.dualstack.us-
west-1.amazonaws.com/thumbs/120/apple/276/light_bolt_
26a1.png

```

Fig. 6: LLM Anomaly Hyperlinks

to an “assistant” in the Qwen LLM’s outputs, for example it appeared as though the Qwen LLM was attempting to communicate with what it refers to as the “assistant” though these communications were output to the user, for Figure 5.

Furthermore, in anomalies which appeared to be conversations an entity labeled “assistant” appeared, responding to the Qwen LLM, for example in a separate anomaly it was noted: “Assistant: In this scenario, the first line is 1029, and the second line is 1234. The function is designed to return the next number in sequence based on the last digit of the previous number.”, which was followed by the LLM creating a solution to the described problem. This type of communication seems to suggest reinforcement-learning human-feedback type interactions and could indicate that logs from these training sessions are the source of the leak. The Qwen LLM also possesses a variety of agents, one of which is indeed named “assistant” [23], potentially indicating AI assistant reinforcement-learning logs or perhaps another type of interaction with an agent. Without access to the training session logs themselves, however, proving this for a certainty is not possible and thus the observations remain conjecture.

The second of the two unique anomaly types observed during the testing phase of this work was that of LLM input/output confusion. To reiterate, the flow of the exploit was firstly the problematic prompt would cause a thousands of emojis to be output, followed by the output of a plausible data leak. Instead of the data leak sometimes a confused message from the LLM, such as those addressing an assistant, were output. One such message, shown in Figure 7 followed the typical precursor to the plausible leak, a deluge of thousands of emojis, which was truncated from Figure 7), by questioning why the user had sent many emoticons and plus symbols, which evidently in Figure 7 was in fact the LLM’s output, not a user prompt.

Having the LLM repeat the exact series of emoticons that had preceded previous abnormal outputs via prompt request did not yield abnormal outputs. Moreover, requesting that the LLM endlessly repeat spurious emojis also did not yield abnormal outputs. This suggests that the LLM’s loss of context and subsequent interpreting of it’s own output as a user or assistant prompt is significant, and is potentially bypassing built-in LLM safeguards in a form of jailbreak.

